

SPIDER

EU-LAC Digital Partnership

D.1.1 – Concept note for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation

Grant Agreement Number: 101135861

Project Acronym: SPIDER

Funding Scheme: Coordination and Support Action

Due date: 30/04/2024

Actual date: 29/04/2024

Document author/s: UPM

Version: 1.0

Dissemination level: PU

Status: Final Version

Document History			
Version	Date	Comments	Author
0.1	13/03/2024	First draft version	Cristina López, Maria F. Cabrera, UPM
0.2	20/03/2024	Second draft version	Cristina López, Maria F. Cabrera, UPM Cristian Patiño, CEDIA
0.3	04/04/2024	Third draft version	Cristina López, Maria F. Cabrera, UPM Cristian Patiño, CEDIA Johanna Füllmann, DLR
0.4	17/04/2024	Fourth draft version	Cristina López, Maria F. Cabrera, UPM Cristian Patiño, Luis Fernando Vargas, CEDIA Johanna Füllmann, DLR
0.5	23/04/2024	Fourth draft revision	Luciana Ayciriex, INMARK
1.0	29/04/2024	Final version	Cristina López, Maria F. Cabrera, UPM Cristian Patiño, Luis Fernando Vargas, CEDIA

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BELLA	Building the Europe Link to Latin America
EU	European Union
LAC	Latin America and the Caribbean
R&I	Research and Innovation
GEANT	Regional Research and Education Networks of Europe
EC	European Commission
ODS	Open Dialogues Sessions
VREs	Virtual Research Environments
NREN	National Research and Education Networks
IADB	Inter-American Development
CAF	Corporación Andina de Fomento
ECLAC	Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean
CELAC	Community of Latin American and Caribbean States
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
AI	Artificial Intelligence
HLPF	High-Level Political Forum
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
FPI	Foreign Policy Instruments
CLF	Community Leaders Forum
eLAC	Digital Agenda for Latin America and the Caribbean
RMIS	Reunión de Ministros del Interior y de Seguridad
MERCOSUR	Southern Common Market
IICA	Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The [SPIDER project](#) aims to maximize the potential of the newly formed “Building the Europe Link to Latin America” (BELLA) network and translate the results of dialogues between the European Union (EU) and Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) into action within the contexts of digitalization in Research and Innovation (R&I). Through strategic engagement, SPIDER will actively involve key R&I stakeholders from the EU and LAC regions in collaborative discussions and the formulation of a unified vision and strategy to fully exploit the capabilities of the [BELLA network](#) and implement digital dialogue outcomes, thereby strengthening EU-LAC cooperation in R&I. By exploring the actual policies, infrastructures, and collaborative frameworks, this document underscores the significance of enhancing EU-LAC cooperation for driving innovation, economic growth, and social development.

In response to the evolving landscape of digitalization in R&I, the SPIDER project strategically positions itself to leverage the BELLA network and EU-LAC dialogues' outcomes to promote collaborative efforts in digital transformation. This concept note delineates the framework that underpins EU-LAC cooperation, offering a roadmap for synergistic engagement across geographic and strategic domains.

In the exploration of definitions and key concepts, the document provides a clear explanation of digital transformation, highlighting its transformative impact on societies, economies, and governance structures. Furthermore, it offers an overview of the BELLA network and its infrastructure, emphasizing its critical role in bridging the digital divide between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean, facilitating knowledge exchange, and driving socio-economic development.

A comprehensive review of current bi-regional and national policies, strategies, and funding programs in R&I reveals opportunities and challenges for fostering collaboration. The analysis underscores the importance of aligning policies and investments to promote cross-border cooperation and address common challenges in digital transformation.

Through a participatory process involving data collection and workshops, the concept note identifies common goals and strategies for collaboration in digital transformation between the EU and LAC regions. It highlights the synergies between initiatives such as BELLA, ResInfra, EU-LAC Foundation, and EU-LAC Digital Acceleration, underscoring the potential for enhanced collaboration and knowledge exchange.

The scope of cooperation is defined by delineating the geographic and strategic domains of the SPIDER project. It emphasizes the importance of engaging stakeholders from diverse sectors and regions to maximize the impact of collaborative efforts. Additionally, the document outlines 6 technology areas identified by SPIDER that can take advantage of BELLA to support the digital transformation: Artificial Intelligence (AI), 5G, blockchain, cloud computing, cybersecurity, and Virtual Research Environments (VREs).

Finally, qualitative indicators for outcome assessment are developed to monitor dialogue outcomes and assess implementation progress. These indicators reflect stakeholder satisfaction, policy influence, sustainability, knowledge exchange, and technological innovation, providing valuable insights for optimizing the impact of dialogue initiatives.

In conclusion, the SPIDER project represents a unique opportunity to foster collaboration in digital transformation between the EU and LAC regions. By leveraging the BELLA network and other regional initiatives, the project aims to drive innovation, knowledge exchange, and socio-economic development in both regions, while remaining adaptable to emerging developments in EU-LAC cooperation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The SPIDER project aims to support the exploitation of the full potential of the newly established BELLA network and the implementation of the outcomes of EU-LAC dialogues in the context of digitalisation in R&I. Within the context of the project, this concept note is formulated to outline the framework that will serve as the foundation for enhancing EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation.

1.1. Purpose of the concept note

This document aims to present a revision of current bi-regional and national policies, strategies, and funding programs in R&I, and to identify synergies and commonalities that could facilitate collaboration on digital transformation, leveraging the infrastructure provided by BELLA. The concept note was developed collaboratively with consortium partners to ensure a co-creative process that addresses the needs of all work packages and aligns with the overarching vision of the SPIDER project.

It provides an explanation of the concept of digital transformation and an overview of the BELLA network and its infrastructure. Regarding the cooperation framework, it defines the geographic and strategic scope, identifies BELLA countries and their roles, and describes the selected technology areas for collaboration.

Furthermore, qualitative indicators are presented to assess and monitor the implementation status of dialogue outcomes across the BELLA countries in the EU-LAC regions. These indicators will serve as valuable tools for evaluating the progress of collaborative efforts facilitated by BELLA infrastructure.

By leveraging secondary data sources such as the ResInfra EU-LAC map of National and Regional Research Infrastructures policies and the outcomes of Task 1.2 “Mapping key dialogues’ commitments and thematic priorities for the digital transformation”, this concept note provides a comprehensive framework for guiding the review process and facilitating informed decision-making.

1.2. Importance of EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation

Cooperation between EU-LAC on digital transformation is essential to foster innovation, drive economic growth, and address common challenges. By sharing knowledge, expertise, and resources, both regions can leverage each other's strengths to develop new technologies, create digital solutions, and enhance productivity in the field of R&I. This collaborative effort enables the sharing of best practices, the development of tailored solutions to address regional challenges, and the empowerment of marginalized communities through improved access to digital tools and resources.

To achieve EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation, it is essential to exploit the full potential of the BELLA network, because its high-performance communication infrastructure connects academic and research institutions across Europe and LAC, facilitating collaboration in R&I. BELLA also promotes digital inclusion by bridging the digital divide and enables joint efforts to address global challenges such as climate change and cybersecurity.

By working together, EU and LAC countries can unlock the transformative potential of digital technologies, ensuring that the benefits of the digital age are accessible to all individuals and communities, regardless of their background or geographic location.

2. DEFINITIONS AND KEY CONCEPTS

2.1. *Digital transformation*

In the context of research, innovation, and international cooperation, digital transformation refers to the strategic integration of digital technologies and practices to enhance collaboration, accelerate discovery, and drive innovation across borders. It encompasses not only the adoption of digital tools and technologies but also the cultural and organizational changes necessary to leverage them effectively.

Digital transformation in research involves leveraging technologies such as cloud computing, big data analytics, artificial intelligence, and collaborative platforms to revolutionise how scientific research is conducted, shared, and applied. It enables researchers to collect, analyse, and share vast amounts of data more efficiently, leading to new insights and breakthroughs in various fields. Through digital platforms and networks, researchers can connect and collaborate across geographic boundaries, sharing expertise, resources, and data to address complex global challenges collaboratively.

Overall, it is essential for driving scientific progress, fostering collaboration, and addressing global challenges effectively in the digital age. By embracing digital technologies and a culture of collaboration, researchers and institutions can unlock new opportunities for research and make a more significant impact on society.

2.2. *The BELLA network*

The [BELLA network](#), short for "Building the Europe Link to Latin America," is a high-capacity research and education network connecting Europe with Latin America and the Caribbean. This ambitious initiative, funded by the European Commission and by a consortium made up of the Regional Research and Education Networks of Europe (GEANT), from Latin America (RedCLARA) and the NRENs (National Research and Education Networks) of Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, France, Germany, Italy, Portugal, and Spain, aims to enhance collaboration in research, education, and innovation between the two regions.

It was launched in 2016 by the European Commission, alongside several Latin American and Caribbean countries, as part of the Horizon 2020 program, with the aim of building a dedicated high-capacity research and education network. The initial phase of the BELLA project focused on deploying a submarine fiber-optic cable connecting Europe with Latin America and the Caribbean, significantly increasing internet capacity and reliability for academic and research institutions in the region. This infrastructure laid the groundwork for fostering greater cooperation and knowledge exchange across borders. As the demand for advanced networking capabilities continued to grow, the BELLA program adapted to meet the evolving needs of the research and education communities. In 2021, the European Commission (EC) and Latin American partners announced the launch of BELLA II, building upon the achievements of the first phase and expanding the scope of the network, specially to Caribbean countries.

BELLA II initiative aims to further enhance connectivity and collaboration by deploying additional infrastructure, such as high-speed links and network services, to support emerging research areas and address new challenges in fields like artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and digital humanities. Moreover, the program emphasizes capacity building and knowledge sharing initiatives to ensure that institutions across Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean can fully leverage the benefits of advanced networking technologies.

It facilitates seamless communication and collaboration among researchers, educators, and students, enabling them to work together on data-intensive research projects, share resources, and access specialized tools and services. This network bridges the digital divide between Europe and LAC by providing equitable access to digital resources and opportunities for collaboration. By extending high-speed connectivity to underserved areas in LAC, BELLA aims to promote digital inclusion and empower communities to participate fully in the global knowledge economy. It is a catalyst for innovation and economic development in both regions.

2.2.1 BELLA governance

The BELLA governance model is predicated on achieving consensus among stakeholders for the digital ecosystem's sustainability and growth, emphasising collaborative interactions across three operational levels:

- Political/Strategic
- Planning/Management
- Operational

These tiers of governance are intricately interconnected and interdependent.

The governance is structured considering organisational strategies and operational architecture. Key to this structure is the involvement of various stakeholders, including a collegiate body of triple helix leaders, RedCLARA's pivotal negotiation role, and the Executive Directorate's coordination efforts. These components work together to ensure sustainable development, foster innovation, and maintain the digital ecosystem's integrity.

Furthermore, organisational strategies and operational architecture are meticulously designed to align with the ecosystem's goals, promoting collaboration, ensuring data integrity and universal access. Infrastructure development, interoperability, and efficient service delivery are underscored, alongside the importance of clear operational guidelines and ethical data practices that govern the operation and behaviour of ecosystem participants. Ultimately, this governance model seeks to create a transparent, accountable, and inclusive digital ecosystem that supports innovation and societal benefits, anchored by strong stakeholders' engagement.

3. METHODOLOGY TO CREATE THE CONCEPT NOTE

In line with the overall methodology of the SPIDER project, the initial activities related to establishing the framework of collaboration have followed Design Thinking's human-centered problem-solving approach. The application of [Design Thinking](#) principles has ensured that the definition of key concepts, analysis of the current landscape, co-creation of indicators, and the establishment of geographical scope and cooperation strategies align with the needs and vision of all project partners, as well as other BELLA stakeholders targeted to engage in SPIDER activities.

Moreover, the human-centered approach has been applied throughout the process, such as when gathering the vision of the project partners as preliminary information that could contribute to mapping the landscape of ideas pertaining to the enhancement of EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation.

To achieve this, the following methods and tools have been employed:

- Online preparatory meetings to define the objectives of the activities and elaborate the necessary materials in each case (e.g., XML templates, boards, trigger questions, etc.), as well as to collect the results and write reports distributed to all consortium members. For instance, the XML templates were distributed through the email communication channel and became useful to collect preliminary information on the vision of each partner, serving as input to plan subsequent collaborative activities.
- The consortium's Google Drive folder as a reference location to store all preparatory materials, as well as result reports, enabling easy access to the information generated throughout the process.
- Focus group sessions on hybrid workshop format, with participants representing the vision of each partner, where their vision and experience were shared to analyze and become aware of the current landscape regarding EU-LAC cooperation, as well as to brainstorm ideas that drive such partnership. In these sessions, tools like [Miro](#) were used, with pre-designed boards to facilitate collaboration and effectiveness of the process, as well as to foster teamwork among participants. These tools visually represent the feedback and provide valuable insights into the current state of the art, challenges, and potential areas for improvement in fostering innovation and digital transformation in the EU-LAC cooperation. The workshop discussions were guided by the principles put forth by Bohm, Williams, and Yankelovich, emphasizing open and meaningful communication, deep listening, and collective exploration of complex topics. Participants were encouraged to suspend judgment, engage in active listening, explore new modes of communication, and engage in inquiry and reflection.

4. STATE OF THE ART OF POLICIES AND FUNDING PROGRAMMES

4.1. Review of current bi regional and national policies, strategies and funding programmes related to R&I

In order to review the state of the art in policies and funding programs related to R&I, SPIDER will conduct a mapping of dialogues and agreements in deliverables D1.2 and D1.3 “Mapping of digital dialogues and identified EU-LAC agreements”, complementing the framework outlined in this concept note. The mapping will encompass both bi-regional and national levels, focusing on policies, strategies, and funding programs within the EU and LAC. By doing so, we seek to gain insights into the current landscape of digital transformation, identifying key commitments arising from bi-regional, bilateral, and multilateral dialogues. This approach will enable us to pinpoint opportunities for collaboration between the EU and LAC, ultimately enhancing cooperation in R&I.

Through a screening process, SPIDER also analyses key commitments resulting from digital dialogues between Europe and LAC countries such as Brazil, Mexico and Argentina (i.e. Argentina Digital Agenda 2030) as well as commitments coming from more multilateral dialogues such as the Pacific Alliance, MERCOSUR Digital, EU-LAC Digital Economy Dialogue, EU-LAC Digital Alliance, Digital Agenda for LAC (2024), EU-CELAC Strategic Roadmap on STI (2021-2023) and BELLA’s Open Dialogues Sessions (ODS). The screening process of dialogues includes different types of documents such as declarations, position papers, action plans and roadmaps.

In total, between 8 and 10 dialogues, and between 50-120 bilateral, regional and multilateral agreements are to be analysed. One key information from this task is the identification of the main actors involved in digital dialogues and agreements to support the survey on “Digital Ecosystem Interconnectivity in LAC and EU” under task 2.1 “Assessment of the full potential of BELLA infrastructure”. The first version of the mapping will be delivered in the first six months of the project and a more comprehensive mapping is then due further towards the end of the project.

In general, the review comprises common bi-regional thematic priorities related to digital transformation technologies identified by SPIDER such as AI, 5G, Blockchain, Cloud Computing, Cybersecurity and VRE (see section 6.2 “Description of technology areas for collaboration”). However, specific other like-minded “key and buzzwords” will also be examined, depending on the dialogues/agreements focus and labelling of key transformation set of vocabulary.

In this context, the following table presents an initial compilation of dialogues and agreements that have been identified for further analysis. The table includes the name of each dialogue or agreement (Table 1 and Table 2 respectively), a brief description, the region it impacts, the key actors involved, and the achieved outcomes.

Dialogue name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
High-Level Political Forum (HLPF) on Sustainable Development	The HLPF is the central United Nations platform for the follow-up and review of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at the global level.	Globally	United Nations	Summary by the President (HLPF 2021) Summary by the President (HLPF 2022) Summary by the President (HLPF 2023)
Fourth meeting of the Conference on Science, Innovation and Information and Communication Technologies of the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean	The ECLAC views science, technology and innovation as a fundamental enabler of and driving force for the productive transformation needed by the countries of the region to achieve much sought-after sustainable and inclusive development.	LAC	ECLAC	Science, technology and innovation for sustainable and inclusive productive development. Guidelines for 2024-2025
Thirty-ninth session of ECLAC	In a highly complex macroeconomic, social and environmental context in the region that demands a rethinking of short- and long-term public policies, the ECLAC is fulfilling its mandate at its thirty-ninth session, by presenting the countries of the region with a proposal for economic reactivation and transformation of development models in Latin America and the Caribbean.	LAC	ECLAC	Towards transformation of the development model in Latin America and the Caribbean: production, inclusion and sustainability
VIII Summit of Heads of State and Government of the	The Heads of State and Government of the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States (CELAC) met in Kingstown, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines on March 1, 2024, in furtherance their commitment to strengthen integration and give a united	LAC	CELAC	Declaration of Kingstown

Dialogue name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
Community of Latin America and Caribbean States (CECLAC)	voice through consultation, concertation and political dialogue to the multiplicity of challenges, opportunities and strengths facing the region.			
European Council meeting (21 and 22 March 2024)	The European Council held an exchange of views with the UN Secretary-General António Guterres on the geopolitical situation and key global challenges. The European Council marked the 30th anniversary of the EEA Agreement with the Prime Ministers of Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway	EU	Council of the European Union	European Council meeting (21 and 22 March 2024) – Conclusions
EU-CELAC Summit	<p>The EU-CELAC Summit takes place on 17-18 July 2023 in Brussels, Belgium.</p> <p>The third EU-CELAC summit brings EU leaders and leaders from the CELAC together. The Summit is co-chaired by Charles MICHEL, President of the European Council; and Ralph GONSALVES, President of CELAC and Prime Minister of Saint Vincent and the Grenadines.</p> <p>The leaders discuss opportunities offered by the green and digital transitions to increase prosperity, with the principles of a fair, social and just transformation central to the talks.</p> <p>During the summit, leaders broach a wide range of topics with a view to further strengthening the EU-CELAC partnership, including: enhanced cooperation in multilateral fora; global peace and stability; trade and investment; economic recovery; efforts to combat climate change; research and innovation; justice and security for citizens.</p>	EU-LAC	Council of the European Union and CELAC	Declaration of the EU-CELAC Summit 2023
EU-CELAC Ministerial meeting	Ministers of foreign affairs from the EU and the CELAC met for the third time on 27 October 2022 in Buenos Aires, holding	EU-LAC	Council of the European	Co-Chairs' Communiqué (press release) CELAC–EU 3rd Foreign Ministers Meeting

Dialogue name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
	discussion around the theme "Renewing the bi-regional partnership to strengthen peace and sustainable development".		Union and CELAC	BI-REGIONAL ROADMAP 2022 - 2023
Informal meeting of heads of state or government	EU leaders discussed long-term priorities with regard to enhancing the EU’s strategic autonomy. They adopted the Granada declaration, in which they outlined key priorities and actions to make Europe a strong, dynamic and competitive power. The President of the European Council adopted a declaration on migration.	EU	European Union	Declaration by the President of the European Council The Granada declaration
EU-LAC High-Level event on Human Development and Health 2023	Represents an important step in the 2023/2025 EU-CELAC roadmap agreed during the last July’s 2023 III EU-CELAC Summit, where Heads of State from both sides of the Atlantic committed to renewing the bi-regional long-standing partnership founded on shared values, interests and strong economic, social and cultural ties.	EU-LAC	Council of the European Union and CELAC	-
DIALOGUE ON SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS - EU - Latin America and the Caribbean Dialogues on Sustainable Food Systems	<p>EU-LAC Dialogues on Sustainable Food Systems are organised, aiming to promote a constructive exchange of ideas to find common grounds, principles, and initiatives that can pave the way for collaboration to push food systems towards sustainability.</p> <p>These Dialogues are organised with the support of the Foreign Policy Instruments (FPI) and the EU-LAC Policy Dialogue Facility. They will consist of a total of four sub-regional workshops, and concluding with a bi-regional conference expected to take place at the end of 2022</p>	EU-LAC	European Union and MERCOSUR	<p>PRESS RELEASE POLICY DIALOGUES EU-COLOMBIA, ECUADOR, PERÚ ON SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE AND FOOD SYSTEMS</p> <p>PRESS RELEASE Building Sustainable Food Systems Together. The European Union, MERCOSUR countries and Chile cooperate towards Sustainable Food Systems for the benefit of farmers, consumers, and the environment.</p> <p>PRESS RELEASE Building Sustainable Food Systems</p>

Dialogue name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
				Together. European Union and Central America cooperating towards Sustainable Food Systems for the benefit of farmers, consumers, and the environment.
EU-LAC High-level Policy Dialogue on digital policy and regulations	It consists of a high-level policy dialogue between the EU and LAC on digital policy and regulation at ministerial and senior official level. The dialogue will help both regions to see the other as a key partner and, by supporting Latin American regional digital integration, build convergence on key policies.	EU-LAC	European Commission	-
EU-CELAC Ministerial meeting	Ministers of foreign affairs from the EU and the CELAC met for the third time on 27 October 2022 in Buenos Aires, holding discussion around the theme "Renewing the bi-regional partnership to strengthen peace and sustainable development".	EU-LAC	Council of the European Union and CELAC	BI-REGIONAL ROADMAP 2022-2023 Co-Chairs' Communiqué (press release) CELAC–EU 3rd Foreign Ministers Meeting
Meeting of the European Political Community	The European Political Community aims to foster political dialogue and cooperation to address issues of common interest strengthening the security, stability and prosperity of the European continent. This platform for political coordination does not replace any existing organisation, structure or process and does not aim to create new ones at this stage.	EU	Council of the European Union	Remarks by President Charles Michel ahead of the second European Political Community meeting (june 2023, october 2023, oncoming july 2024)
Summit of Presidents of Mercosur	Summit of Heads of State of Mercosur and Associated States and Mercosur and Associated States.	LAC	MERCOSUR	Special Declaration of the Presidents of MERCOSUR on Democracy and the Integrity of

Dialogue name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
				Information in Digital Environments
Research Software Funders Forum	The Research Software Funders Forum is a collaboration of funding organisations committed to supporting research software, and those who develop it, as fundamental and vital to research. It provides a formal mechanism for funders to share practices and consider how to address common challenges to achieve the significant cultural change needed across the research sector globally.	Globally	Research Software Alliance	Research Software Funding Opportunities Research institution policies to support research software - Collection
Community Leaders Forum	The Community Leaders Forum (CLF) offers an opportunity for participants to meet other community leaders, engage in interactive discussions, and consider how to address common issues to achieve shared goals. The CLF is one of the online forums that ReSA hosts for decision makers and key influencers in the global research software community.	Globally	Research Software Alliance	Notes of Research Software Community Leaders Forum
BELLA II Strategic Dialogues	<p>BELLA II is a regional initiative that aims to reduce the digital divide and support the development of the necessary infrastructure to consolidate and expand a digital ecosystem of science, technology, education, and innovation.</p> <p>It seeks to strengthen and expand the digital ecosystem of Latin America and the Caribbean, enabling relations and exchanges between companies, research centres, educational institutions and national research and education networks, which are aligned with the strategic objectives in education, science, technology and innovation from LAC and Europe.</p>	EU-LAC	RedCLARA	<p>Outcomes Report: BELLA II Strategic Dialogues Workshop</p> <p>Outcomes Report Dialogue on the Challenges and Opportunities of the Digital Transformation in Latin America and the Caribbean</p> <p>EU-CELAC Summit Workshop: Strategic dialogues for the development of the digital ecosystem for the education, research and innovation in Latin America and the Caribbean</p>

Dialogue name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
Ibero-American Summit of Heads of State and Government	The Ibero-American Community is advancing in the construction of a roadmap that allows expanding the rights and opportunities of its citizens and finding solutions to the great problems of the region.	Ibero-American States	Ibero-American General Secretariat	Ibero-American Environmental Charter The second is the Ibero-American Charter of Digital Principles and Rights Critical Path to achieve food security. Special Communiqué on International Financial Architecture
EU-LAC Digital Alliance Dialogue on Cybersecurity	During the EU-LAC Digital Alliance days in Colombia in November 2023, senior governmental officials and representatives of regional organisations, academia, CSOs and the private sector agreed that collaboration between LAC and EU is essential to enhance global cybersecurity, and contribute to a free, open, safe and secure cyberspace, including by improving capacities to prevent, manage and mitigate cyber-risks.	EU-LAC	D4D HUB	Agenda Digital Alliance cybersecurity dialogue Last update 310124

Table 1: Interim dialogues mapping

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development	The HLPF is the central United Nations platform for the follow-up and review of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the SDGs at the global level.	Globally	United Nations	Ministerial Declaration (HLPF 2021) and Ministerial Declaration (HLPF 2022)

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability	This Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability builds on actions undertaken by the Research Software Alliance (ReSA), research funding organisations, and the community surrounding it to develop awareness about the role funders can play in sustaining software in the longer term.	Globally	Research Software Alliance	Amsterdam Declaration of Funding Research Software Sustainability Version:0.3 ADORE.software Toolkit
Ibero-American Summit of Heads of State and Government	The Ibero-American Community is advancing in the construction of a roadmap that allows expanding the rights and opportunities of its citizens and finding solutions to the great problems of the region.	Ibero-American States	Ibero-American General Secretariat	III Quadrennial Action Plan of Ibero-American Cooperation (PACCI)
Ministerial Conference on the Information Society in Latin America	The Conference aims to define a set of digital policy priorities at the regional level within the framework of the Digital Agenda for Latin America and the Caribbean (eLAC)	LAC	ECLAC	Montevideo Declaration (2022) Digital Agenda for Latin America and the Caribbean (eLAC2024) Cartagena Declaration (2018) Digital Agenda for Latin America and the Caribbean (eLAC2022)
LXI Summit of Presidents of MERCOSUR	The Presidents of the Argentine Republic, the Republic of Paraguay, the Eastern Republic of Uruguay, the Vice President of the Federative Republic of Brazil, States Parties of MERCOSUR and the High Authorities of the Associated States, meeting in Montevideo, Uruguay, on the occasion of the LXI Summit of Presidents of MERCOSUR, on December 6, 2022	LAC	MERCOSUR	Special Declaration on Culture of the MERCOSUR States Parties and Associated States Special Declaration on Cybercrime of the MERCOSUR States Parties and Associated States
LXIII Summit of Presidents of MERCOSUR	The Presidents of the Argentine Republic, the Federative Republic of Brazil, the Republic of Paraguay, and the Oriental Republic of Uruguay, Member States of MERCOSUR, and the High Authorities of the Associated States, gathered in Rio de	LAC	MERCOSUR	Special Declaration of the MERCOSUR Presidents on Democracy and the Integrity of

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
	Janeiro, Brazil, on December 6 and 7, 2023, on the occasion of the LXIII Summit of MERCOSUR Presidents.			Information in Digital Environments
Reunión de Ministros del Interior y de Seguridad (RMIS)	Meeting of Ministers of the Interior and Security	LAC	MERCOSUR	General Plan of Reciprocal Cooperation and Coordination for Regional Security
Agreement for Cooperation Between Southern Market (MERCOSUR) and the Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture (IICA)	The objective of the agreement is to establish the general bases of technical cooperation to promote the sustainable development of family agriculture and increase its contribution to food and nutritional security and the rural economy in the MERCOSUR Member States.	LAC	MERCOSUR	Agreement for Cooperation Between Southern Market (MERCOSUR) and the Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture (IICA)
Memorandum of Understanding Between Mercosur and the Community of Portuguese Speaking Countries	This Memorandum aims to establish areas and mechanisms of international technical cooperation between the Parties for the development of future actions and/or technical cooperation projects for the benefit of the Member States of both international organisations.	LAC	MERCOSUR and CPLP	Memorandum of Understanding Between Mercosur and the Community of Portuguese Speaking Countries
Memorandum of Understanding of International	The objective of this Memorandum seeks the development of actions, projects, and cooperation programs with a focus on sustainable human development that allows improving the	LAC	MERCOSUR and CAF	Memorandum of Understanding of International Cooperation between the Common Market of

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
Cooperation between the Common Market of the South (MERCOSUR) and the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF)	standard of living, strengthening social and productive structures of excluded communities in the region, and promoting the exchange of good practices and successful public policies that contribute to social inclusion.			the South (MERCOSUR) and the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF)
Memorandum of Understanding between Mercosur and the Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture	Memorandum of Understanding between Mercosur and the Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture	LAC and Ibero-American States	MERCOSUR and OEI	Memorandum of Understanding between Mercosur and the Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture
Cooperation Mechanism between National Data Protection Authorities for Mutual Assistance and Technical, Regulatory and Supervisory Cooperation on	The purpose of this Mechanism is to establish instances so that national authorities in data protection can make the necessary efforts to promote mutual assistance and technical, regulatory and supervisory cooperation in matters of privacy and personal data protection	LAC	MERCOSUR	Cooperation Mechanism between National Data Protection Authorities for Mutual Assistance and Technical, Regulatory and Supervisory Cooperation on the Protection of Personal Data within the framework of MERCOSUR

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
the Protection of Personal Data within the framework of MERCOSUR				
Digital Agenda Group Action Plan 2023-2025	The Action Plan of the Digital Agenda Group (GAD) of MERCOSUR aims to be an instrument that allows unifying different priority initiatives of the Group in the same roadmap that favour the development of the block’s digital policy, these being driven by the coordinated work of specific technical commissions or by different specialised subgroups, on relevant topics such as: the development of digital infrastructure and connectivity in the region; the increase of cross-border trade and the regional digital market; the increase in security in the digital environment; digital signature, digital government; improvement in the measurement of access and use of ICT; the promotion of digital inclusion in the block; and coordination in regulatory aspects and in international forums on agenda topics	LAC	MERCOSUR	Digital Agenda Group Action Plan 2023-2025
TTC Joint Roadmap for Trustworthy AI and Risk Management	The EU-US Trade and Technology Council TTC Joint Roadmap aims to advance shared terminologies and taxonomies, but also to inform our approaches to AI risk management and trustworthy AI on both sides of the Atlantic	EU and US	European Commission	TTC Joint Roadmap on Evaluation and Measurement Tools for Trustworthy AI and Risk Management 1 December 2022 EU-U.S. Terminology and Taxonomy for Artificial Intelligence - Second Edition

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
Regulation on the adoption of a European Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme	The European Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme (EUCC) builds on the Mutual Recognition Agreement ('MRA') of Information Technology Security Certificates of the Senior Officials Group Information Systems Security ('SOG-IS') using the Common Criteria, including the group's procedures and documents.	EU	European Commission	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implementing Regulation on the adoption of a European Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme 2. Annex to the Implementing Regulation on the adoption of a European Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme
The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking	<p>The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking a joint initiative between the EU, European countries and private partners to develop a world-class supercomputing ecosystem in Europe.</p> <p>The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU) is a legal and funding entity, created in 2018 and located in Luxembourg. The EuroHPC JU achieved autonomy in September 2020. The EuroHPC Joint Undertaking allows the European Union and EuroHPC participating countries to coordinate their efforts and pool their resources with the objective of making Europe a world leader in high performance computing (HPC).</p>	EU	European Commission	The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
European Declaration on Quantum Technologies	The signatory Member States recognise the strategic importance of quantum technologies for the scientific and industrial competitiveness of the EU and commit to collaborating on the development of a world-class quantum technology ecosystem across Europe, with the ultimate aim of making Europe the 'quantum valley' of the world, the leading region globally for quantum excellence and innovation	EU	European Commission	European Declaration on Quantum Technologies

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
Advancing 6G: A Vision for Transatlantic Collaboration	Through the Trade and Technology Council (TTC), the U.S. and EU have a unique opportunity to foster collaboration in research and innovation, ensuring that the development and deployment of 6G technology align with shared principles and values.	EU and US	European Commission	U.S.-EU Trade and Technology Council (TTC) - Advancing 6G: A Vision for Transatlantic Collaboration
First Latin American and Caribbean Ministerial and High Level Summit on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence (2023)	<p>With the support of CAF and UNESCO, Chile received ministers and high-level authorities from more than 30 countries in Latin America and the Caribbean in an unprecedented meeting in the region.</p> <p>The Ministers and High Authorities representing the countries of Latin America and the Caribbean, gathered in Santiago de Chile on October 23 and 24, 2023, on the occasion of the Forum on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence in Latin America and the Caribbean, and the Ministerial Summit and High Authorities of Latin America and the Caribbean, which seeks to facilitate the exchange of impressions regarding the challenges and opportunities of the development of artificial intelligence (AI) in the region and discuss ways to address them, including the establishment of a Working Group with a view to the constitution of an Intergovernmental Council of Artificial Intelligence for Latin America and the Caribbean.</p>	LAC	UNESCO and CAF	Santiago Declaration
Decision (EU) 2022/2481 Of The European Parliament And Of The Council of 14 December 2022 establishing the Digital Decade	<p>This Decision establishes the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 and sets out a monitoring and cooperation mechanism for that programme designated to:</p> <p>(a) creating an environment favourable to innovation and investment by setting a clear direction for the digital transformation of the Union and for the delivery of digital targets at Union level by 2030, on the basis of measurable indicators;</p>	EU	European Parliament and Council of the European Union	Decision (EU) 2022/2481 Of The European Parliament And Of The Council of 14 December 2022 establishing the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
<p>Policy Programme 2030</p>	<p>(b) structuring and stimulating cooperation between the European Parliament, the Council, the Commission and the Member States;</p> <p>(c) fostering the consistency, comparability, transparency and completeness of monitoring and reporting by the Union.</p> <p>2. This Decision establishes a framework for multi-country projects.</p>			
<p>Decisions: Council Decision (EU) 2021/764 of 10 May 2021 establishing the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, and repealing Decision 2013/743/EU</p>	<p>This Decision establishes the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (the 'Specific Programme'), as set out in point (a) of Article 1(2) of Regulation (EU) 2021/695.</p> <p>This Decision lays down the operational objectives of the Specific Programme, the budget for the period 2021-2027, the rules for implementation of the Specific Programme and the activities to be carried out under the Specific Programme.</p>	<p>EU</p>	<p>Council of the European Union</p>	<p>Decisions: Council Decision (EU) 2021/764 of 10 May 2021 establishing the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, and repealing Decision 2013/743/EU</p> <p>COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION of 20.3.2024 on adopting the 2025-2027 strategic research and innovation plan under the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation</p> <p>ANNEX: Commission Implementing Decision adopting the 2025-2027 research and innovation strategic plan under the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe -</p>

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
				The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation
EuroLat Resolution: on international cooperation and multilateralism in a COVID-19 context	EUROLAT – Resolution of 27 July – Madrid based on the report by the Committee on Political Affairs, Security and Human Rights on international cooperation and multilateralism in a COVID-19 context	EU-LAC	EURO-LATIN AMERICAN PARLIAMENTARY ASSEMBLY	EuroLat Resolution on international cooperation and multilateralism in a COVID-19 context
EuroLat Resolution: on Bi-regional cooperation for the strengthening of health systems, for access to and distribution of vaccines, and for scientific research to face pandemics	EUROLAT – Resolution of 27 July 2023 – Madrid based on the report by the Committee on Social Affairs, Youth and Children, Human Exchanges, Education and Culture Bi-regional cooperation for the strengthening of health systems, for access to and distribution of vaccines, and for scientific research to face pandemics	EU-LAC	EURO-LATIN AMERICAN PARLIAMENTARY ASSEMBLY	EuroLat Resolution: on Bi-regional cooperation for the strengthening of health systems, for access to and distribution of vaccines, and for scientific research to face pandemics
EU-Latin America and Caribbean Digital Alliance	EU-LAC Digital Alliance creates a strategic framework to foster substantial bi-regional cooperation across the full spectrum of digital and space issues. The Alliance's aim is to foster the development of secure, resilient and human-centric digital infrastructures on the basis of a values-based framework, ensuring a democratic and transparent enabling environment and putting a strong emphasis on privacy and digital rights. It is the first intercontinental digital partnership agreed between both	EU – CELAC	European Commission	EU-Latin America and Caribbean Digital Alliance EU 2030 Digital Compass EU-LAC Digital Accelerator Expanding the BELLA programme

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
	regions under Global Gateway investment strategy, the EU's offer for trusted and sustainable connections with partner countries.			Establishing a regional Copernicus strategy
Conference on the Future of Europe	The Conference on the Future of Europe was launched in March 2021 as a joint undertaking of the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union and the European Commission, to listen to European citizens and let them have their say on the future of Europe, through a citizen-led series of debates and deliberations. The focus is now on the follow-up.	EU	Council of the European Union	Putting Vision into Concrete Action (2022) Commission work programme 2023 Conference on the Future of Europe - Proposals and related specific measures contained in the report on the final outcome of the Conference on the Future of Europe: Updated assessment
CAF Chile Country Strategy 2023-2026	Since Chile’s reintegration into CAF, one of the most notable news of the last 20 years of the bank, CAF’s programmatic work in the country has focused on becoming a relevant actor for its sustainable and balanced development. To this end, it has strived to generate spaces for exchange and technical dialogue backed by the support of CAF’s specialised areas, showing various actors, public and private, its experience and timely and relevant response capacity to contribute to the development agenda driven by the Government of Chile	LAC	CAF	CAF Chile Country Strategy 2023-2026
CAF Colombia Country Strategy 2023-2026	Since its founding in 1968, CAF, the development bank of Latin America and the Caribbean, has supported Colombia by financing large-scale programs and projects, and strengthening technical and regulatory capacities for the implementation of high-impact public policies.	LAC	CAF	CAF Colombia Country Strategy 2023-2026

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
Partnership for Development in Latin America and the Caribbean	CAF -the development bank of Latin America and the Caribbean- and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) have signed a framework agreement on procedures that will allow both institutions to collaborate more agilely in generating knowledge, providing technical assistance, and financing instruments to offer comprehensive solutions with local impact in alignment with the national development priorities of the countries in the region.	LAC	CAF and UNDP	Framework Agreement CAF-UNDP
Partnership for Development in Latin America and the Caribbean	The Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) reaffirmed their long-standing cooperation through a new framework agreement to foster enhanced collaboration through harmonising operational and procurement processes for more efficient cooperation and accelerating sustainable development in Latin America and the Caribbean.	LAC	IDB and UNDP	Framework Agreement IDB-UNDP
GovTech Global Partnership	To support countries in adopting sound practices and solutions in GovTech, and to ensure a broad global partnership for effective exchange and transfer of knowledge and good practice, the GovTech Global Partnership (GTGP) was first established by the World Bank's Governance Global Practice partnership with the Government of Switzerland, Austria, and Korea in 2019. The GTGP is a multi-stakeholder initiative that includes advanced and aspiring GovTech countries, development partners, private sector, academia, civil society, and others involved in the GovTech domain.	Globally	WORLD BANK, CAF and Ministries (Korea, Austria, Switzerland)	GovTech Global Partnership
EU Policy and Outreach Partnership in South America	The main goal of this project consists in supporting the achievement of EU Foreign Policy objectives by implementation by strengthening the EU's ability to engage with different audiences and stakeholders in third countries through Public Diplomacy. In this sense, it expects to further develop the EU's	EU-LAC	OEI and EU	EU Policy and Outreach Partnership in South America

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
	soft power by enhancing widespread understanding and visibility of the EU and its role on the world scene, through public diplomacy and outreach activities on issues relevant to the bilateral relations specifically with Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Peru and possibly other countries in South America.			
Framework agreement OEI- EU-CELAC Foundation	Framework agreement establishing the bases of cooperation for the development of programmes and activities of mutual interest, especially in the areas of education, science, culture and research.	Ibero-American States and EU	OEI and EU-LAC Foundation	Framework agreement OEI- EU-CELAC Foundation
Program for the Strengthening of Science and Technology Systems (FORCYT)	FORCYT is an initiative of the Organization of Ibero-American States (OEI) and the European Union (EU), co-financed by the EU's Transition Development Facility	EU-LAC	OEI and EU	
Cooperation Agreement	CAF, Development Bank of Latin America, and the Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture (OEI) signed a non-reimbursable technical cooperation agreement on Thursday to support the Project for the Promotion and Articulation of Innovation Ecosystems in Latin America	LAC	OEI and CAF	Cooperation Agreement OEI - CAF
Global Gateway in Latin America and the Caribbean	Global Gateway projects are developed and delivered jointly by Team Europe, which consists of the EU institutions, Member States, European financial institutions working together with European businesses, governments, civil society and the private sector in partner countries. Global Gateway seeks to create a partnership where the public sector of Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean link up	EU-LAC	European Commission	EU-LAC Global Gateway Investment Agenda

Agreement name	Description	Region of impact	Main actors	Main outcomes
	with the private sector to generate business investments to contribute to wealthier societies to the benefit of all.			
Collaboration agreement to jointly deepen bi-regional relations between Latin America, the Caribbean and Europe	For both SEGIB and the EU-LAC Foundation, committed to multilateral interaction and collaboration, the signing of this agreement is an excellent opportunity to bring the two regions closer together through a range of instruments and joint activities ranging from the organisation and implementation of conferences, seminars and workshops to the production of publications and information relevant to the bi-regional partnership in 2022.	Ibero-American States and EU	SEGIB and EU-LAC Foundation	Joint press release from the EU-LAC International Foundation and the Ibero-American General Secretariat (SEGIB)
Joint Declaration on a partnership between the States Parties to the Framework Agreement of the Pacific Alliance and the European Union	Enhance social, productive and lasting ties, based on the principles of democracy, human rights and rule of law, and a shared vision on open trade and investment, and sustainable development	EU-LAC	EU and Pacific Alliance	Joint Declaration on a partnership between the States Parties to the Framework Agreement of the Pacific Alliance and the European Union
Joint Declaration Pacific Alliance - OECD	Establish solid, productive, strategic and longstanding ties, strengthening cooperation between the Participants based on a shared vision of the benefits of multilateral cooperation, economic integration, the exchange of best practices and the promotion and implementation of OECD standards.	LAC	Pacific Alliance	Joint Declaration Pacific Alliance - OECD

Table 2: Interim agreements mapping

The aforementioned compilations of dialogues and agreements provide an overview of the existing landscape pertaining to the advancement of EU-LAC cooperation in digital transformation. This comprehensive analysis will be subject to a meticulous review in Deliverable 1.2 “Mapping of digital dialogues and identified EU-LAC agreements” (Interim version). For the final iteration of this mapping, specific criteria will be employed to select and further analyse the dialogues in question.

Furthermore, the forthcoming information, namely the details regarding the Information Collected (Section 4.2) and the SPIDER Workshop (Section 4.3), will contribute to the development of a conceptual framework aimed at fostering enhanced EU-LAC cooperation in the domain of digital transformation.

4.2. Collecting information and key findings

On December 6th, 2023, an XML document was distributed via email to the consortium partners with the aim of gathering preliminary information that could contribute to mapping the landscape of ideas pertaining to the enhancement of EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. This document served as a revision of the categories previously discussed in bi-regional dialogues.

The feedback received from the partners and other key actors was subsequently uploaded to the SPIDER Drive folder and organised into mind maps within the Miro platform. The visual representation of this feedback can be observed in the images of Annex 1.

The information gathered reflects ideas related to regional policies, strategies, drivers, actors, initiatives, barriers, and dialogues in the context of research, innovation, and digital cooperation between the EU and LAC. These mind maps provide valuable insights into the current state of collaboration, challenges, and potential areas for improvement in fostering innovation and digital transformation in the EU-LAC partnership.

The feedback highlights several key themes and ideas. Firstly, it underscores the importance of establishing a human-centric vision of the digital economy and society, which prioritises inclusivity, accessibility, and social impact. This vision is supported by building a secure digital backbone connectivity and promoting open science and innovation.

Secondly, it identifies various main drivers and actors in the EU-LAC collaboration. These include policy level representatives, members of bilateral projects, EU delegations in LAC, National Research and Education Networks (NREN), private sector entities such as tech corporations with data centres in LAC, and international organisations like the Inter-American Development Bank (IADB) and the Corporación Andina de Fomento (CAF). The involvement of these stakeholders is crucial for driving innovation and implementing joint initiatives.

Thirdly, it highlights the existence of diverse initiatives and programs aimed at strengthening research and innovation ecosystems in both regions. These initiatives encompass funding programs by IADB and CAF, national plans for science, technology, and innovation, and collaborative networks such as the International Development Research Centre (IDRC) program for inclusive science and innovation in Latin America.

Furthermore, the feedback shed light on the main barriers and challenges faced in the EU-LAC collaboration. These include insufficient funding, political changes leading to discontinuity of commitments, lack of harmonisation between regulations, and the absence of a systemic and centralised common approach. Divergent regulatory frameworks and unequal partnerships are also identified as obstacles to effective cooperation.

In conclusion, the information collected provides a comprehensive overview of the current landscape of research, innovation, and digital cooperation between the EU and LAC. They highlight the need for a human-centric approach, strong collaboration among diverse

stakeholders, and the resolution of existing barriers. By addressing these challenges and leveraging the identified drivers and initiatives, the EU and LAC can foster innovation, bridge the digital divide, and create a thriving ecosystem for research and development.

4.3. Workshop and insights

On December 14th, 2023, the inaugural SPIDER online workshop was conducted with the following objectives:

1. To facilitate a brainstorming session focused on identifying the necessary measures to enhance EU-LAC cooperation in the realm of digital transformation.
2. To promote collaboration and teamwork among participants.

The workshop was attended by 19 members representing various partner institutions within the SPIDER consortium. The meeting was conducted via a 2-hour [Zoom](#) session. It drew upon previous bi-regional dialogues and initiatives, such as the BELLA II EU-CELAC Summit Workshop: Strategic Dialogues for Ecosystem Development for education, research, and innovation in Latin America and the Caribbean. These experiences informed the proposed methodology for the SPIDER workshop.

Likewise, to promote effective teamwork, participants were divided into four breakout groups, each assigned to a specific category. A Miro board was used as a collaborative tool for brainstorming within these categories, aligning with the objectives of WP1 “Framework for enhancing EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation” and Deliverable D1.1 “Concept note for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation”

Figure 1: Miro Board

A total of 189 ideas were proposed in 8 dimensions: actors (39), barriers (27), needs and expectations (34), new categories (15), opportunities (21), strengths (23), success cases (13) and weaknesses (17).

The contributions reflect a range of ideas and perspectives on the topic at hand. The identified actors include academia, the private sector (including industry and companies), NRENs, telecommunication companies, policy level representatives, and public institutions. Specifically, it is crucial to highlight the significant role of NRENs in coordinating alongside a wide range of key actors in the region. They play a paramount role in facilitating and capitalising on collaborative efforts, thereby contributing to the realisation of desired outcomes.

Barriers that were frequently mentioned by the participants encompassed the lack of funding, lack of knowledge and understanding of previous experiences, the relevance of digital transformation, and technical knowledge gaps. Policy issues and the potential impact of political changes were also acknowledged as significant challenges to be addressed.

The needs and expectations expressed by the participants revolved around strengthening initiatives such as BELLA and fostering partnerships between the EU and LAC countries. Additionally, there was an emphasis on gaining a comprehensive understanding of the impact of previous commitments and projects.

Participants also proposed new categories for consideration, including quantum technologies, opportunities for collaboration, strategic partnerships, knowledge sharing, and success cases. Notably, the initiatives BELLA and ResInfra were highlighted as examples of successful endeavours.

Identified weaknesses centred around disparities in infrastructure and the lack of harmonisation of policies and regulations. These factors were seen as obstacles to achieving effective collaboration and cooperation.

Overall, the participants' contributions provide valuable insights into the various dimensions of the topic, shedding light on the actors involved, barriers faced, needs and expectations, new categories of focus, opportunities, success cases, and weaknesses that need to be addressed to foster fruitful collaboration in the field.

5. SYNERGIES AND COMMONALITIES FOR EU-LAC COLLABORATION IN DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

5.1. Identification of common goals and strategies

The Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC), also known as CEPAL, is a regional commission of the United Nations that was established in 1948. Its objective is to contribute to the economic development of the region and strengthen economic ties within the region and with other nations.

Similarly, the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States (CELAC) is another significant regional organisation within the United Nations system. Its aim is to promote cooperation, dialogue, and collaboration among LAC countries. CELAC focuses on addressing common challenges and enhancing economic and social development in the region.

Both ECLAC and CELAC play crucial roles in defining policies and guidelines for the development of LAC. They prioritise various initiatives such as sustainable development and integration, sustainable tourism as a positive instrument for poverty eradication, gender equality and women's empowerment, digital transformation and inclusion, environmental sustainability and climate change mitigation, health and education, social development and economic stability, food security, and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and space cooperation. CELAC also focuses on fostering digital inclusion, innovation, and meaningful connectivity, through a people-centric lens.

Likewise, the EU was established to oversee economic and political integration. Among its seven official institutions, the European Council plays a significant role in bringing together EU leaders and defining the general political direction and priorities of the EU. Several key areas emerge as focal points for the EU. Firstly, there is a strong emphasis on competitiveness, highlighting the importance of strengthening the EU's global competitive edge by fortifying its industrial foundation in alignment with the accelerated twin green and digital transitions. Secondly, research, innovation, and digital transformation are actively supported through initiatives like Horizon Europe aiming to achieve sustainable development goals and emphasising evidence-based approaches to inform public policies. Thirdly, the EU prioritises initiatives aimed at transitioning towards a green and digital economy, including policies that support renewable energy, foster digital skills, and facilitate infrastructure development, all with a steadfast commitment to sustainable consumption and production. Additionally, education and vocational training are given high priority, advocating for lifelong learning and the seamless integration of digital competencies. The EU also places great importance on fostering international partnerships and cooperation, particularly in addressing shared global challenges such as climate change and digital inclusivity. Policies promoting social inclusion, gender equality, and the empowerment of marginalised groups are integral components of the EU's approach to sustainable development. Furthermore, the European Council places significant focus on ICT and space cooperation, including space regulation and cybersecurity considerations. Digital transformation is deemed of utmost importance, ensuring inclusiveness, trustworthiness, and a human rights-based approach to artificial intelligence and emerging technologies, all while striving towards the goals set forth in the 2030 Digital Decade. Cybersecurity stands as another critical area of focus, with the EU actively implementing its cybersecurity strategy and working towards greater strategic autonomy in the realm of digital technologies.

In this context, commonalities arise between the regions, including sustainable development, digital transformation and inclusion, environmental sustainability and climate action, social development and inclusion, gender equality, and international

partnership and cooperation. This common ground presents potential areas of collaboration, such as knowledge sharing and best practices exchange related to sustainable development models, digital transformation strategies, and social inclusion policies. Moreover, joint research and innovation projects can be pursued, focusing on climate change, renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and digital skill development. Partnerships can facilitate technology transfer and capacity building, particularly in areas like sustainable energy solutions, agriculture, and digital infrastructure development. Strengthening regional integration between LAC and EU across diverse sectors is also worth exploring. Collaborative climate action initiatives can address climate adaptation, mitigation, and disaster risk reduction. Lastly, working together to tackle global issues such as cybersecurity, food security, and migration can contribute to collective efforts.

Besides, the convergence of various initiatives aimed at fostering digital transformation between EU and LAC regions presents significant opportunities for collaboration. Examining the objectives of these initiatives alongside the goals of the SPIDER project, reveals several synergies and commonalities.

[BELLA](#) is a cornerstone initiative that lays the foundation for enhanced connectivity between research and education networks across EU and LAC countries. Its infrastructure provides a vital link for knowledge exchange and collaboration, facilitating the flow of information and expertise crucial for digital transformation efforts. Complementing BELLA, the [ResInfra](#) project focuses on enhancing research infrastructure in LAC countries. Through identifying and improving existing research facilities, it supports scientific collaboration and innovation, fostering an environment conducive to technological advancement and digitalization.

Moreover, the [EU-LAC Digital Accelerator](#) serves as a catalyst for digital innovation and entrepreneurship. By connecting digital innovation hubs, startups, and research institutions, this network creates synergies that drive technological advancement and economic growth across both regions.

Finally, [EU-LAC Foundation](#) focuses on promoting the adoption of open source software and collaboration in this domain. By fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration in open source development, this initiative contributes to digital sovereignty, innovation, and competitiveness in the EU and LAC regions.

By leveraging the resources, networks, and collaborative spirit fostered by initiatives like BELLA and others, SPIDER amplifies its impact, driving forward the agenda of digital transformation and cooperation between EU and LAC stakeholders. These initiatives are an opportunity for collaboration, innovation, and progress in the digital age through their interconnected efforts and shared objectives.

5.2. Analysis of how BELLA network supports digital transformation collaboration

The BELLA infrastructure plays a vital role in supporting digital transformation collaboration by providing high-speed, reliable, and secure connectivity between Europe and LAC. Here are some aspects and real initiatives on how it facilitates collaboration in the context of digital transformation:

- **High-Speed Connectivity:** BELLA offers high-capacity internet connectivity, enabling researchers, educators, and innovators on both continents to exchange data, share resources, and collaborate in real-time. This high-speed connectivity accelerates the pace of collaboration, allowing researchers to access and analyse large datasets, run complex simulations, and engage in interactive communication seamlessly. For example, researchers from European universities have collaborated with counterparts in Latin America to study biodiversity conservation in the Amazon rainforest. With high-speed connectivity provided by BELLA, researchers can remotely access and analyse satellite imagery, sensor data, and climate models, leading to more comprehensive insights into ecosystem dynamics and informing conservation efforts.
- **Advanced Networking Technologies:** The BELLA network leverages advanced networking technologies, including fiber-optic cables and state-of-the-art infrastructure, to ensure fast and reliable data transmission. These technologies support the transfer of large volumes of data between Europe and LAC, facilitating collaborative research projects, joint initiatives, and knowledge exchange activities. BELLA has promoted open data sharing and collaboration by providing researchers with access to shared data repositories and collaborative platforms. For instance, researchers studying climate change have used BELLA infrastructure to access and share climate datasets collected from monitoring stations across Europe and Latin America. This open data sharing fosters transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration in scientific research, leading to more robust and actionable insights into global environmental challenges.
- **Virtual Research Environments:** BELLA infrastructure enables the creation and operation of VREs, digital platforms that provide researchers with integrated tools, resources, and services for collaborative research. VREs hosted on the BELLA network offer researchers from Europe and LAC access to shared data repositories, collaborative workspaces, and analytical tools, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and accelerating research workflows. For example, medical researchers have used BELLA infrastructure to share medical imaging data and collaborate on clinical trials for novel treatments. This collaboration has led to advancements in healthcare delivery, improved patient outcomes, and enhanced access to medical expertise across regions.
- **Secure Communication:** BELLA ensures secure communication and data transmission through robust cybersecurity measures, protecting sensitive research data, intellectual property, and critical infrastructure from cyber threats. By providing a secure and trusted environment for collaboration, BELLA infrastructure builds confidence among stakeholders and encourages greater participation in collaborative research and innovation initiatives. BELLA has enabled international education collaboration by connecting students and educators across Europe and Latin America. Universities on both continents have collaborated to offer joint courses and research programs, allowing students to participate in virtual classrooms and collaborative projects. BELLA infrastructure ensures reliable

connectivity and seamless communication, providing students with access to diverse perspectives and expertise from different cultural backgrounds.

- **Cross-Border Collaboration:** The BELLA network facilitates cross-border collaboration by connecting researchers, educators, and innovators across Europe and LAC, regardless of geographical location. This enables diverse teams to collaborate on joint research projects, share expertise, and leverage complementary strengths, driving innovation and fostering mutual understanding between regions. For instance, researchers studying climate change have used BELLA infrastructure to access and share climate datasets collected from monitoring stations across Europe and Latin America. This open data sharing fosters transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration in scientific research, leading to more robust and actionable insights into global environmental challenges.

Overall, BELLA infrastructure serves as a catalyst for digital transformation collaboration by providing the foundational connectivity and advanced networking capabilities necessary to support collaborative research, innovation, and education initiatives between EU and LAC. Through its high-speed connectivity, advanced technologies, and secure communication channels, BELLA network empowers stakeholders to harness the full potential of digital technologies and drive positive social, economic, and scientific outcomes.

6. SCOPE OF COOPERATION

6.1. *Defining the geographic and strategic scope*

With a focus on optimizing BELLA network, SPIDER's geographic and strategic scope is designed to include the BELLA countries to support the socio-economic progress across EU and LAC regions. At the core of the strategy lies a collaborative agreement with RedCLARA and GEANT, key stakeholders in research and education network advancement. This partnership aims to amplify the impact of BELLA, empowering academia, as well as the public and private sectors, to harness its potential for regional development.

Four esteemed members of RedCLARA - RNP (Brazil), REUNA (Chile), CEDIA (Ecuador), and RedCONARE (Costa Rica) - are part of the SPIDER consortium. Their involvement underscores a commitment to facilitating effective utilization of BELLA infrastructure. Moreover, a SPIDER's Twinning Programme will be implemented as a strategic initiative to unlock collaboration and innovation opportunities. By selecting ten digital innovation hubs (five from the EU and five from LAC) for twinning, the programme will foster synergies and facilitate knowledge exchange. These hubs will benefit from BELLA infrastructure, supported by tailored services to nurture their growth and impact.

The project activities will promote the interconnection of regional and national research and education networks, exemplified by RedCLARA. Spanning Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Chile, Ecuador, Guatemala, Honduras, Mexico, Nicaragua, and Uruguay, RedCLARA is crucial for collaboration and knowledge sharing. Its integration with GEANT further enhances connectivity, enabling seamless collaboration between EU and LAC partners.

The BELLA II initiative, launched in 2021, brings together eleven European and Latin American NRENs, including prominent entities from Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, Germany, Italy, Portugal, and Spain. The geographical distribution of stakeholders targeted to engage in SPIDER activities aligns with the expansion of BELLA II's scope, aiming to encompass countries in Central America and the Caribbean such as Peru, El Salvador, Honduras, and Guatemala, thus fostering unprecedented inclusivity and collaboration.

SPIDER collaborators possess an exceptional and extensive web of influential decision-makers and visionaries within regional and national RENS, research and innovation communities, and the EU-LAC digital innovation ecosystem. This strong network will serve as an amplifier to disseminate SPIDER initiatives and outcomes throughout pertinent stakeholder groups.

6.2. *Description of technology areas for collaboration*

SPIDER will promote the adoption and use of digital transformation technologies that can benefit from the BELLA potential to support R&I projects and initiatives for EU-LAC cooperation.

The initial six focus areas that the project will take into account are:

- **Artificial Intelligence (AI):** this area involves the development of computer systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and language translation. AI is crucial for digital transformation in EU-LAC cooperation in R&I because it enables automation, optimization, and innovation across various sectors, from healthcare and agriculture to manufacturing and finance. AI-powered tools can analyse large datasets, identify patterns, and generate insights, facilitating more informed decision-making and accelerating the pace of research and innovation.

- **5G:** it refers to the fifth generation of mobile network technology, offering significantly faster data speeds, lower latency, and greater capacity compared to previous generations. 5G plays a pivotal role in driving progress and fostering collaboration because it enables high-speed, reliable, and low-latency connectivity, facilitating real-time collaboration, data sharing, and experimentation across borders. With 5G networks, researchers can remotely access and manipulate large datasets, conduct experiments using IoT devices, and collaborate with colleagues worldwide, fostering greater innovation and knowledge exchange.
- **Blockchain:** it is a decentralized and distributed ledger technology that enables secure and transparent recording of transactions across multiple parties. Blockchain is an important area because it enhances trust, transparency, and accountability in collaborative research projects and innovation ecosystems. By providing an immutable record of data and transactions, blockchain technology can help address issues such as data integrity, intellectual property rights management, and fraud prevention, thereby fostering greater confidence and collaboration among stakeholders.
- **Cloud Computing:** this area involves the delivery of computing services, including storage, processing, and networking, over the internet on a pay-as-you-go basis. It is critical for digital transformation because it provides scalable and flexible infrastructure for storing, managing, and analyzing large volumes of data and running compute-intensive simulations and experiments. Cloud services enable researchers to access advanced computing resources and software tools without the need for significant upfront investment, lowering barriers to entry and promoting collaboration among institutions and researchers.
- **Cybersecurity:** it encompasses technologies, processes, and practices designed to protect computer systems, networks, and data from unauthorized access, cyberattacks, and data breaches. Cybersecurity is an indispensable area because it safeguards sensitive research data, intellectual property, and critical infrastructure from cyber threats, ensuring the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of information. Strong cybersecurity measures build trust and confidence among stakeholders, enabling secure collaboration, data sharing, and innovation across borders.
- **Virtual Research Environment:** this field includes digital platforms or ecosystems that provide researchers with integrated tools, resources, and services for conducting collaborative research and managing research workflows. VREs are important in R&I because they enable seamless and efficient collaboration, communication, and knowledge sharing among geographically dispersed researchers and institutions. By providing access to shared data repositories, collaborative workspaces, and analytical tools, VREs facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration, accelerate research workflows, and enhance the productivity and impact of research initiatives.

These focus areas will be reviewed as the project evolves to better match the digital transformation landscape, based on insights from surveys, focus groups and call for ideas on future use of BELLA.

7. QUALITATIVE INDICATORS FOR OUTCOME ASSESSMENT

7.1. Development of indicators to monitor dialogue outcomes

In order to establish qualitative indicators for the assessment and monitoring of dialogue outcomes implementation in EU-LAC, a workshop was conducted on February 23rd, 2024, in Madrid. This workshop adopted a collaborative approach, integrating ideas generated during a brainstorming session centered around six key questions, resulting in the creation of three qualitative indicators for each question, aided by artificial intelligence within the context of the ideas proposed in the workshop. The outcomes are available for reference in Annex 2.

Figure 2: Indicators Miro Board

The trigger questions were strategically positioned within a Miro Board to stimulate the ideation process among participants. The qualitative indicators derived from the collaborative co-creation process offers valuable insights into assessing and monitoring the implementation of dialogue outcomes across the BELLA countries in LAC. One of the fundamental reflections drawn from these indicators is the critical role of **stakeholder satisfaction and engagement**. By measuring stakeholders' satisfaction levels and their active involvement in the dialogue process, essential feedback is gathered to evaluate the effectiveness and inclusivity of the dialogue initiatives. This underscores the importance of fostering collaborative relationships and ensuring that diverse voices are heard throughout the implementation process.

Besides, the emphasis on **assessing policy influence and long-term impact** highlights the need for dialogue outcomes to drive meaningful changes and sustainable improvements in targeted areas. It is important to not only track immediate policy changes but also evaluate the lasting effects of dialogue initiatives, ensuring their relevance and

effectiveness over time. Furthermore, the incorporation of expert opinions and the exploration of existing best practices and frameworks underscore the importance of drawing on diverse sources of knowledge and experiences. By leveraging insights from experts and established evaluation criteria such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Development Assistance Committee (DAC) Criteria, stakeholders can enrich their understanding of dialogue outcomes implementation and adapt strategies accordingly. This reflective approach ensures a robust foundation for assessing the multifaceted aspects of dialogue initiatives and optimizing their impact.

Lastly, the consideration of technology as a facilitator for data collection, analysis, and reporting underscores the potential for leveraging digital tools to streamline processes and enhance collaboration. By measuring the **interoperability between different technological platforms and the availability of project management tools**, the importance of investing in technology infrastructure is highlighted to support efficient data management and decision-making processes. This technological integration can strengthen the overall monitoring and evaluation framework, enabling stakeholders to track progress more effectively and make informed adjustments as needed.

In conclusion, the reflection on these qualitative indicators underscores the importance of stakeholder engagement, policy influence, sustainability, knowledge exchange, and technological innovation in driving successful dialogue outcomes implementation across the BELLA countries in LAC. By embracing these insights, stakeholders can enhance their capacity to assess, adapt, and optimize dialogue initiatives for meaningful and lasting impact.

It is important to acknowledge that these indicators may require adaptation and customization to align with the specific context and objectives of the assessment. The findings present an initial collection of generic qualitative metrics that can be further tailored to address the unique requirements of the project. Furthermore, these indicators shed light on the significance of technology in facilitating the gathering, analysis, and reporting of data pertaining to the qualitative indicators employed for evaluating the implementation of dialogue outcomes.

7.2. Assessing and monitoring implementation with indicators

The qualitative indicators obtained from a co-creation process based on six questions have the potential to provide a comprehensive and detailed view of the implementation status of dialogue outcomes. These indicators offer a variety of perspectives to understand the effectiveness and impact of ongoing dialogue initiatives.

Given the diversity in the typology of the indicators, their application in SPIDER project activities can vary significantly. For example, in some cases, we might opt to conduct structured interviews or questionnaires to assess stakeholder satisfaction levels or to measure stakeholders' perception and satisfaction regarding the implementation of dialogue outcomes. These tools would provide a detailed understanding of participants' opinions and perceptions, which could directly inform about the impact and effectiveness of dialogue initiatives.

In other cases, we might resort to deeper and more detailed analyses to evaluate the long-term impact of dialogue outcomes. This could involve conducting case studies, analyzing historical data, or tracking progress over time to determine if sustainable changes are being achieved in the specific areas identified by the dialogue.

Furthermore, the selection of the application methodology will also depend on the specific indicator and the context in which the dialogue is being implemented. For example, to assess the quality of dialogue, we could use focus groups or content analysis to better

understand the nature and effectiveness of the conversations held during the dialogue process.

In summary, the qualitative indicators offer a wide range of tools and approaches to assess and monitor the implementation of dialogue outcomes. By adapting the application methodology to each specific indicator and relevant context, we can obtain a more comprehensive and detailed understanding of the impact and effectiveness of dialogue initiatives in the EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation.

8. CONCLUSIONS

This concept note establishes the framework of the SPIDER project, which represents a significant step towards enhancing cooperation between the EU and LAC in the field of digital transformation. In this document, the purpose and importance of this initiative is outlined, as well as the key concepts related to digital transformation and the infrastructure provided by the BELLA network.

The need to review current policies and funding programs in R&I at regional and national levels is identified, along with the importance of collecting information and organizing workshops to engage relevant stakeholders in the project development process. The proposed methodology is based on a collaborative and co-creative approach, aiming to ensure that the project's strategies and actions align with the needs and visions of all consortium partners.

The identification of synergies and common areas for collaboration in digital transformation, coupled with the analysis of support provided by BELLA, highlights the importance of leveraging existing resources and regional initiatives to amplify the impact of SPIDER. Moreover, the scope of cooperation is defined geographically and strategically, establishing a solid foundation for promoting collaboration between the EU and LAC in specific technological areas such as artificial intelligence, 5G, blockchain, cloud computing, cybersecurity, and virtual research environments. Finally, the development of qualitative indicators to assess and monitor dialogue outcomes underscores the project's commitment to transparency, accountability, and continuous improvement in the implementation of its objectives.

Establishing the framework of the SPIDER project is an important initial step for clearly and effectively defining upcoming activities, although it is understood that this definition may evolve to adapt to emerging developments in EU-LAC cooperation for digital transformation. This ensures that the SPIDER project represents a unique opportunity to foster collaboration in digital transformation between the EU and LAC, leveraging the infrastructure of BELLA and other regional initiatives to drive innovation, knowledge exchange, and socio-economic development in both regions.

Annex 1

The complete report from partners Excel feedback and the online workshop on 14th of December 2023 is available at:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1guAfpZ8mb7mugjk4_66Z3dJZrvxlyrfG/view

Have you participated in Dialogues for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. If yes, indicate the name and year of dialogue	Please indicate current bi regional and/or national policies, strategies and funding programmes related to R&I	Name the most important actors to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main drivers to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main barriers to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation
Participated in two bilateral dialogues projects, one related to innovation policies and the other innovation and business cooperation: EU-CELAC Innov-AL Platform and ENRICH in LAC		Policy level representatives, EU Delegations in LAC, DG Regio, private sector, bilateral projects members	Reaching common development and innovation areas and building agreements to the implementation	Lack of funding, diverse initiatives thus lacking a systemic and centralised common approach, knowledge and commitment usually lost when projects end, so it is important to create and consolidate sustainable actions that can continue after the end of the funded projects

Have you participated in Dialogues for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. If yes, indicate the name and year of dialogue	Please indicate current bi regional and/or national policies, strategies and funding programmes related to R&I	Name the most important actors to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main drivers to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main barriers to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation
Participation in 4 projects linked to R&I or business cooperation between EU-LAC, including on digital transformation: INCOBRA (2016-2019); ENRICH in Brazil/LAC (2017-2023); EU-LAC ResInfra (2020-2023) and Innov-AL (2018-2021)	Roadmap for implementation of EU-CELAC Action Plan on R&I EU-CELAC Joint Initiative on Research and Innovation (JIRI) EU-LAC Digital Alliance EU-LAC Joint Declaration on Digital Alliance EU-LAC Digital Accelerator D4D Hub in LAC	Members of the BELLA Programme Members of the EU-LAC Digital Accelerator Ella Link Red Clara GEANT COPERNICUS IADB CAF Tech Corporates (especially those with Data centres in LAC, such as Google or Amazon in Ceará, for example)	human-centric vision of the digital economy and society in which the design, development, governance, and use of technology are guided by universal human rights and fundamental freedoms. a) the extension of the BELLA fibre-optic cable to interested countries, building secure digital backbone connectivity and bringing the research communities of the EU and LAC closer together. b) the including two regional Copernicus data centres in Panama and Chile; and High Performance Computing, IoT, Big Data, Cloud	

Have you participated in Dialogues for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. If yes, indicate the name and year of dialogue	Please indicate current bi regional and/or national policies, strategies and funding programmes related to R&I	Name the most important actors to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main drivers to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main barriers to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation
<p>Several EU-Brazil STI Joint Steering Committee Meetings (2014-2021) and the 1st EU-LAC Innovation Cooperation Conference held on 21 and 22 November 2019 in Brussels</p>			<p>proper innovation ecosystem that can provide the necessary support for emerging businesses to grow and scale while offering digital services and solutions and profiting from the digital infrastructure</p>	<p>Political changes and discontinuity of agreed commitments and funding; lack of harmonisation between specific related regulations;</p>
<p>Yes, -Taller Cumbre UE-CELAC: Diálogos estratégicos para el desarrollo del ecosistema digital para la educación, la investigación y la innovación de América Latina y el Caribe (17-07-23) -BELLA II Diálogo Estratégico de Panamá en el marco de la Conferencia TICAL 2023 (15-11-23)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Programa Fortaleciendo sistemas inclusivos de ciencia e innovación en América Latina a través de una red de investigación colaborativa IDRC - BID funding program - CAF funding program - Plan Nacional De Ciencia, Tecnología E Innovación 2022-2027 - Plan Nacional de Desarrollo e Inversión Pública 2023-2026 de Costa Rica 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -State Universities and CONARE -Ministeries (Ministry of Foreign Affairs -Ministry of the Presidency -Ministry of National Planning and Economic Policy -Ministry of Science, Technology and Telecommunications) -Industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Governance between actors (industry, academy, society) -Spaces for discussion and development of policies and initiatives around the topic -Financing in scientific research and innovation projects in digital transformation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Digital divide (access to connectivity and electronic devices to the population) -Contradictory policies and programs -Little to none Technological and Digital education

Have you participated in Dialogues for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. If yes, indicate the name and year of dialogue	Please indicate current bi regional and/or national policies, strategies and funding programmes related to R&I	Name the most important actors to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main drivers to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main barriers to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation
<p>Indirectly through: Study in Europe Fair, Argentina & Brazil https://studyineuropefairs.eu</p>	<p>[1] EU-LAC Knowledge Forum Report: https://eulacfoundation.org/sites/default/files/2023-06/EU-LAC_Knowledge_Forum_Report_EN.pdf</p> <p>[2] Policy Recommendations on Innovation Collaboration between the EU and LAC: https://www.eucelac-platform.eu/sites/default/files/documents/policy_recommendations_-_innovation_forum_vf_0.pdf</p> <p>[3] EU-CELAC ResInfra Project: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871140</p> <p>[4] EU-LAC Digital Alliance: https://d4dhub.eu/events/eu-lac-digital-alliance</p>	<p>Some actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) • Latin American and Caribbean Network for Democracy (REDLAD) • EU Companies with presence in LAC ie Indra • D4D Hub https://d4dhub.eu/lac 	<p>-Shared economic interests: Europe and Latin America have a history of economic interdependence, and the EU is the main investor in the region, with nearly 700 billion euros invested</p> <p>-Promoting open science and innovation: The EU-LAC Knowledge Forum Report emphasises the importance of developing joint policies to promote open science based on the 'FAIR' principles</p> <p>- Promoting multi-stakeholder partnerships, Strengthening digital infrastructure and connectivity, reducing inequality and fostering social inclusion:</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Divergent Regulatory Frameworks 2. Unequal Partnerships: Cooperation requires innovative approaches based on equal partnerships at all levels 3. Need for Greater Connectivity

Have you participated in Dialogues for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. If yes, indicate the name and year of dialogue	Please indicate current bi regional and/or national policies, strategies and funding programmes related to R&I	Name the most important actors to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main drivers to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main barriers to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation
<p>EU-CELAC STI Senior Officials Meetings since 2010 until 2016 (they have a dedicated bi regional thematic working group on ICT)</p> <p>EU-CELAC Working Group on Research Infrastructure (co organised event with RedCLARA in the framework of ResInfra EU-LAC project)</p>	<p>Horizon Europe: Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) + cascading grants, Erasmus+, BID, CAF, AECID (Development cooperation)</p>	<p>European Commission (DG CONNECT, DG INTPA), CELAC pro-tempore presidency.</p> <p>EU-LAC Foundation.</p> <p>STI Ministries, Industry + funding agencies.</p> <p>Enterprise Europe Network ICT sector Group (brokerage events)</p>	<p>European Commission (DG CONNECT, DG INTPA), CELAC pro-tempore presidency.</p> <p>EU-LAC Foundation.</p> <p>STI Ministries, Industry + funding agencies.</p> <p>Multilateral Dialogue on Principles and Values in International R&I Cooperation</p> <p>Enterprise Europe Network ICT sector Group (brokerage events)</p>	<p>There are no known spaces for dialogue where priority areas for cooperation are defined. Actors attending the meetings do not necessarily represent the country's priorities. Many changes in country authorities/embassy representatives. The agreements resulting from the dialogues are not known. The results of the dialogues and agreements are not translated into concrete actions.</p>

Have you participated in Dialogues for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. If yes, indicate the name and year of dialogue	Please indicate current bi regional and/or national policies, strategies and funding programmes related to R&I	Name the most important actors to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main drivers to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main barriers to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation
<p>EU-CELAC STI Senior Officials Meetings since 2011 until 2023 (digital transformation is one of the priority topics under the pillar of global challenges, the bi-regional thematic working group on ICT has been ended)</p> <p>EU-CELAC Working Group on Research Infrastructure (co organised event with RedCLARA in the framework of ResInfra EU-LAC project)</p>		<p>Global Service Facility of the EC (contract: Support to the EU-CELAC Joint Initiative on Research and Innovation)</p> <p>ENRICH in LAC</p> <p>LAC NCP Network</p>	<p>European Commission (DG RTD) through the JIRI SOM & Global Service Facility</p>	
<p>El Diálogo sobre Políticas de Ciberseguridad de la Alianza Digital UE-ALC, 2024</p> <p>Jornadas de la Alianza Digital UE-ALC, Cartagena 2023</p>	<p>Efforts are underway to prioritise inclusive and secure regulations in the rollout of 5G technology, aiming to address gender disparities that hinder women's opportunities in the region.</p>	<p>Stakeholders including national governments, multilateral organisations, academy, and the broader public</p>	<p>Digital transformation can be driven by several key factors: common interests, agreements and alliances, cooperation programs and research and development initiatives.</p>	<p>Digital gaps, lack of financing and resources, Cultural and Linguistic differences, different regulatory frameworks.</p>

Have you participated in Dialogues for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. If yes, indicate the name and year of dialogue	Please indicate current bi regional and/or national policies, strategies and funding programmes related to R&I	Name the most important actors to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main drivers to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main barriers to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation
<p>Dialogue on the Challenges and Opportunities of the Digital Transformation in Latin America and the Caribbean, Montevideo, November 16th, 2022 Open dialogue on digital transformation and the role of the higher education institutions. Havana, December 7th, 2022 BELLA II Strategic Dialogue Workshop, Panama, November 15th, 2023</p>	<p>Horizon Europe. The European Framework Program for Research and Innovation for the period 2021-2027 EU-LAC Digital Alliance EUROsociAL Erasmus+. EU-Cuba 2021-2027 Multiannual Indicative Program, providing support for the creation of sustainable municipalities and the maximisation of the potential of all economic factors in key sectors; focused on agricultural, energy, IT, culture and biotechnology</p>	<p>The academic and the scientific sector Government and policy makers on technological, scientific, research, cooperation, Internationalisation, public administration and social benefits areas International bodies for cooperation and funding, UE delegations and experienced organisations on developing and implementation of cooperation program with LAC countries IT enterprises related with digital transformation</p>	<p>Regional strategies and policies Agreements on cooperation and political dialog Alliances between the public and private sectors Financing programs. Digital development projects, development of digital skills and strengthening of technological infrastructures. Forums, conferences, events and workshops as mechanisms to promote the collaboration on digital transformation</p>	<p>Digital Divide. Equitable access and development of digital skills. Differences in regulatory frameworks and policies related to Information and Communication Technologies can make cooperation harder on issues such as cybersecurity, data protection and governance. Non-robust and outdated infrastructures (such as broadband networks, high-performance computing and data storage and processing) Linguistic and cultural diversity in the countries of both regions. (Communication, and knowledge transfer) Cybersecurity.</p>

Annex 2

QUESTION	INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION
<p>How can we ensure that the defined indicators accurately reflect the progress and impact of dialogue outcomes implementation?</p>	Stakeholder Satisfaction	Measure the satisfaction levels of stakeholders involved in the dialogue process. This can be done through surveys or interviews to gather feedback on their perception of the outcomes and their impact.
	Policy Influence	Assess the extent to which the dialogue outcomes have influenced policy-making processes and decisions. This can be measured by tracking the adoption or integration of dialogue recommendations into policies or actions taken by relevant authorities.
	Collaborative Relationships	Evaluate the strength and effectiveness of collaborative relationships established through the dialogue process. This can be done by assessing the level of trust, cooperation, and ongoing engagement among stakeholders involved in implementing the dialogue outcomes.
<p>What specific aspects or factors should be considered when defining qualitative indicators for assessing the status of dialogue outcomes implementation?</p>	Stakeholder Perception	Measure the perception and satisfaction of stakeholders involved in the dialogue process regarding the implementation of outcomes. This can be done through surveys, interviews, or focus groups to gather their opinions and feedback.
	Expert Opinion	Seek expert opinions on the relevance and effectiveness of the implemented dialogue outcomes. Experts can provide valuable insights and assessments based on their knowledge and experience
	Long-Term Impact	Evaluate the long-term impact of the dialogue outcomes by assessing whether they have led to sustainable changes or improvements in the targeted areas. This can involve analysing data, conducting case studies, or tracking progress over time.
<p>What strategies or approaches can be used to effectively</p>	Stakeholder Engagement	Measure the level of engagement and participation of key stakeholders in the dialogue process. This can include assessing the diversity of stakeholders involved, their active involvement in discussions, and their contribution to decision-making processes.

QUESTION	INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION
monitor and track the progress of dialogue outcomes implementation using qualitative indicators?	Quality of Dialogue	Evaluate the quality of dialogue by assessing factors such as inclusivity, respect for different perspectives, and the ability to reach consensus or make informed decisions. This indicator can help gauge the effectiveness of the dialogue process in promoting meaningful and constructive conversations.
	Implementation of Recommendations	Track the extent to which the recommendations generated through the dialogue process are being implemented. This can involve monitoring the adoption of recommended actions, the allocation of resources, and the progress made towards achieving the desired outcomes.
How can stakeholders actively participate in the process of defining and utilising qualitative indicators to assess and monitor the status of dialogue outcomes implementation?	Stakeholder Engagement	Measure the level of engagement and participation of key stakeholders in the dialogue process. This can include assessing the diversity of stakeholders involved, their active involvement in discussions, and their contribution to decision-making processes.
	Communication Channels	Evaluate the effectiveness and transparency of communication channels established for stakeholders. This can be measured by assessing the clarity, accessibility, and frequency of communication between stakeholders and the implementing body. Feedback mechanisms, workshops, and collaborative data collection can be used to gather insights on the quality of communication channels
	Impact on Policies/Strategies	Assess the extent to which stakeholders perceive a direct relation between their national policies/strategies and the dialogues. This can be measured through surveys, interviews, or focus groups to gather stakeholders' perspectives on how the dialogue outcomes have influenced policy-making processes
Are there any existing best practices or frameworks that can guide the development and utilisation of qualitative indicators for assessing dialogue outcomes implementation in similar contexts?	Intercultural Dialogue Index (ICDI)	This index can be used as a qualitative indicator to assess the level of intercultural dialogue and understanding achieved within a specific context. It measures factors such as cultural diversity, inclusivity, and the effectiveness of communication channels.
	OECD DAC Criteria	The OECD Development Assistance Committee (DAC) Criteria can serve as a qualitative indicator to evaluate the impact and effectiveness of development projects or initiatives. These criteria include relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability, which can be adapted to assess the implementation of dialogue outcomes.
	OECD Guidelines	The OECD guidelines provide a framework for applying evaluation criteria thoughtfully in the context of development projects. These guidelines can be used as a qualitative indicator to assess the thoughtful application of evaluation criteria in monitoring and evaluating the implementation of dialogue outcomes.

QUESTION	INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION
<p>What role can technology play in facilitating the collection, analysis, and reporting of data related to the qualitative indicators used to assess dialogue outcomes implementation?</p>	<p>Interoperability between different technological platforms</p>	<p>This indicator measures the extent to which different technological platforms used for data collection, analysis, and reporting can seamlessly communicate and exchange information. It assesses the efficiency and effectiveness of the technology infrastructure in facilitating data integration and collaboration among stakeholders.</p>
	<p>Data governance and quality assurance</p>	<p>This indicator measures the extent to which different technological platforms used for data collection, analysis, and reporting can seamlessly communicate and exchange information. It assesses the efficiency and effectiveness of the technology infrastructure in facilitating data integration and collaboration among stakeholders.</p>
	<p>Availability of project management tools</p>	<p>This indicator evaluates the availability and utilisation of project management tools, such as Trello, to facilitate the coordination, tracking, and monitoring of data collection, analysis, and reporting activities. It assesses the efficiency and effectiveness of these tools in streamlining workflows and enhancing collaboration among stakeholders.</p>

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